

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS*

Cations	Ligands					
	1		2		3	
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂
H ⁺	12.06	—	9.85	—	10.25	—
VO ²⁺	11.34	8.59	9.77	9.24	9.88	7.76
Mn ²⁺	6.22	5.88	4.68	4.12	5.00	4.24
Co ²⁺	6.86	6.43	5.25	4.57	5.15	5.07
Ni ²⁺	6.65	5.71	5.95	4.91	5.18	4.74
Cu ²⁺	8.64	7.92	7.75	—	6.90	6.48

* For proton association (H⁺), K₁ corresponds to the species LH, while for metal ions K₁ and K₂ correspond to the species ML₁ and ML₂, respectively.

coumarin derivative could not be evaluated due to the commencement of precipitation at pH ≈ 4.7. With the exception of Mn^{II} complexes, the log K₁ values of the diketone complexes were slightly less than those of the acetophenone and coumarin derivatives. This was probably due to the bigger size of the diketone molecule which caused steric hindrance in the complex formation process.

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References

1. G. RODIGHIERO and C. ANTONELLO, *Bool. Chim. Farm.*, 1958, 97, 592.
2. D. B. INGLE, Ph.D. Thesis, Marathwada University, 1969.
3. S. M. SETHNA, N. M. SHAH and R. C. SHAH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228.
4. N. R. MANJRAMKAR, Ph.D. Thesis, Marathwada University, 1970.
5. H. A. FLASCHKA, "EDTA Titrations", Pergamon, New York, 1978.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., Longmans, London, p. 177.
7. H. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
8. J. B. SCARBOUGH, "Numerical Mathematical Analysis", Oxford University Press, 1930, p. 361.
9. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 2nd. ed., Interscience, New York, p. 683.

Potentiometric and Biocidal Studies of Ternary Complexes of some Transition Metals with *N*-Pyridylanthranilic Acid (NPA) and some Bidentate Ligands

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A survey of the literature reveals the description of chelates of a number of bivalent metals/lanthanide^{1,2} ions with anthranilic acid. The synthesis and chelating behaviour of *N*-phenylanthranilic acid have been investigated by Harris and Sweet³.

In this communication, the synthesis of a new ligand, *N*-pyridylanthranilic acid (NPA) from 2-aminopyridine and *o*-chlorobenzoic acid has been described and its proton dissociation constant (NPA, $pK_1 = 3.46 \pm 0.04$; IMDA, $pK_1 = 3.11 \pm 0.09$, $pK_2 = 9.45 \pm 0.11$) were determined by the method of Chaberck and Martell⁴. The binary and ternary complex formation of some bivalent metals with the synthesised ligand and a number of bidentate ligands have been studied potentiometrically, and the values of formation constants of the resulting complexes, evaluated by the respective methods of Thompson and Loraas⁵ and Ramamoorthy and Santappa⁶, are recorded.

The insoluble ternary complex, 1:1:1 Cu^{II}-NPA-HQ has also been isolated and characterised by elemental analysis and ir spectra. The biocidal activity of metal ions, the ligands, and the Cu^{II} complex towards some selected fungi and bacteria are evaluated (Table 3).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either of BDH or E. Merck grade unless stated otherwise. The metal

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NOTES

nitrate solutions were prepared and standardised⁷. For the potentiometric studies, the solution of IMDA was prepared by direct-weighing and HQ was used as monohydrochloride obtained by adding calculated amount of standard HCl solution in the calculated weighed amount of HQ.

Synthesis of NPA: The light yellow crystalline needle shaped NPA was synthesised⁸ by condensing potassium salt of *o*-chlorobenzoic acid and 2-aminopyridine, m.p. 140° (Found: C, 67.20; H, 4.66; N, 12.99. C₁₂H₁₀N₂O calcd. for: C, 67.28; H, 4.67; N, 13.08%). The 1:1:1 Cu^{II}-NPA-HQ was also analysed (Found: C, 57.40, H, 3.80; N, 9.55; Cu, 14.31. CuC₂₁H₁₅N₃O₃·H₂O calcd. for: C, 57.46; H, 3.87; N, 9.57; Cu, 14.48%).

Potentiometric studies: The potentiometric titrations of metal ions, ligands, binary and ternary systems were carried out employing the technique reported earlier⁸.

Results and Discussion

System 1:1:1 M^{II}-NPA-IMDA/HQH⁺: Curves for the system Cu^{II}-NPA-IMDA/HQH⁺ have been discussed as representative (Figs. 1 and 2); curves for other systems involving Ni^{II}/Zn^{II}/Cd^{II} being similar have been avoided.

An inflection at m=1 in the curve (a) (NPA) and (b) (IMDA) in Fig. 1 and curve (b) (HQH⁺) in Fig. 2, can be attributed to the titration of carboxyproton forming the potassium salt of the respective acids in case of NPA and IMDA, and hydrochlorideproton in case of HQH⁺. Two inflections at m=1 and 3 (curve (c)) in case of 1:1 M^{II}-NPA system may be ascribed to the formation of a soluble 1:1 M^{II}-NPA complex in the lower pH range, undergoing decomposition on further alkalinisation giving metal hydroxide and free ions of the acid in solution.

TABLE 1

System	log K _{M,L}	G° kcal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	log K _{M,L,L'}	G° kcal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
1:1 Cu ^{II} -NPA/1:1:1 Cu ^{II} -NPA-IMDA	2.32±0.06	-8.16	13.24±0.14	-18.04
1:1 Ni ^{II} -NPA/1:1:1 Ni ^{II} -NPA-IMDA	2.20±0.16	-2.99	12.54±0.20	-17.09
1:1 Zn ^{II} -NPA/1:1:1 Zn ^{II} -NPA-IMDA	1.96±0.08	-2.67	12.50±0.18	-17.03
1:1 Cd ^{II} -NPA/1:1:1 Cd ^{II} -NPA-IMDA	1.37±0.16	-1.86	12.37±0.20	-16.86

M = Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}. L = NPA. L' = IMDA.

TABLE 2

NPA		HQ		Cu ^{II} -NPA-HQ	
ν _{max}	Assignments	ν _{max}	Assignments	ν _{max}	Assignments
2760w	NH stretch	3100s	OH	3300b	Splitting of NH
2550w	OH stretch of COOH	3270s	OH stretch	1580s	OH stretch in H-OH
1650b	C=O stretch	1685s	Aromatic	1510s	C=O, C-H
1550s	NH stretch	1510s	—	1390s	M-OH
1400m	—	1660s	C=C	1300m	—
1380s	C-H stretch	1610s	C=N	1135s	M-OH
1000s	C-N stretch			775s	C=O
915s	C-C stretch			590w	M-N
770s	NH rock				
750s	C-H bend				
640m	Pyridyl N			525m	M-O
				475m	

TABLE 3—MINIMUM INHIBITORY CONCENTRATION (MIC in μg ml⁻¹) OBSERVED AGAINST INDICATED FUNGI AND BACTERIA

Compd.	Fungi			Bacteria		
	<i>D. tetramers</i>	<i>A. nigracans</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>B. substilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
Cu(NO ₃) ₂	50	50	—	50	50	50
NPA	12.5	—	—	6.25	6.25	25
HQ	12.5	25	25	12.5	25	—
1:1 Cu ^{II} -HQ	12.5	50	25	12.5	25	50
1:1:1 Cu ^{II} -NPA-HQ	12.5	12.5	12.5	6.25	6.25	—

Fig. 1. System 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -NPA-IMDA : (a) NPA, (b) IMDA, (c) 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -NPA, (d) 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -IMDA and (e) 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -NPA-IMDA, T, T' = theoretical composite curve, (→) appearance of precipitate.

Fig. 2. System 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -NPA-HQ : (a) NPA, (b) HQ, (c) 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -NPA, (d) 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -HQ and (e) 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -NPA-HQ, (→) Appearance of precipitate.

Curve (d) representing the titration of 1 : 1 M^{II} -IMDA system in Fig. 1 and 1 : 1 M^{II} - HQH^+ in Fig. 2, give a well defined inflection at $m=2$ accompanied by the formation of a precipitate in Cu^{II} - HQH^+ system, which may be attributed to the formation of a soluble 1 : 1 M^{II} -IMDA and 1 : 1 M^{II} - HQH^+ complex species in the respective systems.

An inflection at $m=3$ exhibited by the curve (e) (Figs. 1 and 2) can be ascribed to the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 M^{II} -NPA-IMDA/ HQH^+ complex. The formation of a soluble complex 1 : 1 : 1 M^{II} -NPA-IMDA is further evidenced by non-superimposable nature of the composite curve T and T', non-formation of a heterogeneous phase throughout the titration and the development of a characteristic orange-yellow colour of the solution near the inflection. Its formation is further corroborated by the constancy observed in the values of formation constant (Table 1).

In the system 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -NPA- HQH^+ (Fig. 2), a sharp inflection at $m=3$ accompanied by the formation of precipitate, support the formation of a ternary species during which carboxy protons of NPA, phenolic and hydrochloride protons of HQH^+

are made labile. The composition of the proposed 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -NPA- HQH^+ complex has been substantiated by the analytical data.

IR spectra : Ir spectral studies of NPA, HQ, and Cu^{II} -NPA-HQ ternary complex were made (Table 2). The OH stretching frequency at 3 270 cm^{-1} observed in free HQ and the OH (COOH) frequency at 2 500 cm^{-1} and the frequency at 640 cm^{-1} for pyridyl nitrogen in free NPA, are absent in the spectra of the complex, indicating the involvement of phenolic group of HQH^+ , COOH and pyridyl nitrogen of NPA in the complex formation. In place of characteristic frequencies at 2 760, 1 550 and 770 cm^{-1} assigned to the NH in NPA, a new absorption band appears at 3 300 cm^{-1} in the spectra of complex, indicating the participation of NH group in the complex formation. The absorption frequencies at 580, and 525 and 475 cm^{-1} are attributed to M-N and M-O bonds in the complex, respectively. The presence of coordinated water molecule in the complex is revealed by a band occurring at 1 580 cm^{-1} .

On the basis of analytical and ir data the following structure may be proposed for the ternary complex.

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References

1. A. YOUNG and T. R. SWEET, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 800.
2. M. CEVOLA, A. S. THOMPA, A. V. CELLIANO and P. S. GENTILE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 290.
3. W. HARRIS and T. R. SWEET, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **60**, 509.
4. S. CHABERCK and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 5052.
5. L. C. THOMPSON and J. A. LORAAS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 89.
6. S. RAMAMOORTHY and M. SANTAPPA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 381.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1962, pp. 431, 418, 463, 430.
8. S. KHANNA, R. KUMAR and G. K. GHATURVEDI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 766.
9. A. E. MARTELL, S. CHABERCK, JR., S. C. COURTNEY, S. WESTERBACK and H. HYTIAMEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **79**, 3036.

Phytochemical Investigation of *Cassia mimosoides* Linn

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CASSIA mimosoides Linn.¹ (leguminosae) is a small tree occurring throughout India and its roots are extensively used as an indigenous drug in the treatment of spasm of stomach. Literature survey revealed that the roots and seeds of this plant was investigated earlier². A chemical investigation of the aerial parts (leaves and stems) of this plant was, therefore, undertaken.

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The air-dried powdered aerial parts (leaves and stems) of *C. mimosoides* were successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and chloroform. The concentrated petroleum ether extract was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°)-benzene (1:1) mixture afforded a white crystalline solid, m. p. 88°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 300 cm^{-1} ; m/z 452 (M^+), 434, and 421. It was identified as n-hentriacontanol by the usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with an authentic sample.

The concentrated chloroform extract of the defatted aerial parts was subjected to chromatographic separation over silica gel with solvents of increasing polarity. The benzene-chloroform (1:1) eluate furnished a yellow solid, m.p. 195°, $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ (M^+ 254); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 660 (non-chelated C=O) and 1 625 cm^{-1} (chelated C=O). It responded to methanolic magnesium acetate test³ for anthraquinones and was characterised as chrysophanol⁴ by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with an authentic sample. Continued elution of the column with the same solvent mixture yielded a very small amount of a solid which crystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow leaflets, m.p. 160-2°, $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ (M^+ 284); $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 257, 267, 275 sh, 283, 390, 415 and 435 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 670, 1 638 and 1 675 cm^{-1} . It responded to the test³ for anthraquinone. Further characterisation of this solid was not possible due to paucity of the material.

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References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 54.
2. S. S. SUBRAMANIAN and S. NAGARJAN, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1970, **32**, 70.
3. L. NIHOUL, *J. Pharm. Belg.*, 1960, **15**, 49.
4. H. HEILBRON and H. N. BUNBURY, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Eyre and Spottiswoods, London, 1965, Vol. 2, p. 707.

Chemical Examination of *Ammannia baccifera* Linn. (Lythraceae)

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AMMANNIA baccifera Linn., (family: Lythraceae) is an important medicinal plant. Survey of literature reveals that no work has been reported so